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Article in IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy · October 2024

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Comparative Evaluation of Converter Control Impact on Torsional Dynamics of Type-IV Grid-Forming Wind Turbines

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Abstract—This paper explores the impact of back-to-back converter control strategies on the torsional dynamics of grid-forming permanent magnet synchronous generator wind turbines (GFM-WTs). Two general converter control methods for GFM-WTs, distinguished by the placement of dc-link voltage control (DVC)—either in the machine-side converter or the grid-side converter, are evaluated through the complex torque coefficient method to offer a theoretical basis. It reveals that a negative damping is introduced when the DVC is with the machine-side converter. Then, to further characterize the parametric impacts of electrical and mechanical system constants and controller gains, the sensitivity analysis is performed by employing the partial derivative algorithm, which is based on the feedforward neural network training. It is found that the converter control has a limited impact on the damped frequency in both GFM converter control methods. Finally, electromagnetic simulations based on full-order nonlinear models of GFM-WTs are carried out to confirm the theoretical findings.

Index Terms—Grid-forming, permanent magnet synchronous generator, torsional dynamics, feedforward neural network.

I. INTRODUCTION

Converter-based resources, particularly wind energy, have been increasingly deployed for transitioning to a decarbonized power system [1]. To facilitate this transition, there is an increasing demand from grid operators to furnish grid-forming (GFM) capabilities with converter-based resources [2]. Recent studies have explored the integration of GFM control with wind turbines [3], especially for type-IV wind turbines, i.e., GFM permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG) wind turbines (GFM-WTs) [4]. Unlike traditional grid-following (GFL) wind turbines (GFL-WTs), which rely on the grid to establish voltage and frequency, GFM-WTs can actively

stabilize the grid by providing voltage and frequency support [5], [6]. Nonetheless, this integration poses several technical challenges, among others, the electromechanical dynamics of GFM-WTs, particularly torsional vibrations caused by grid-side dynamics, while minimal in traditional GFL-WTs, can significantly affect the lifespan of WTs and induce power oscillations that might compromise grid stability in GFM-WT applications, as shown in Fig. 1 [7], [8].

Fig. 1. Unstable GFM-WT under 2° grid phase step disturbance [8].

Existing studies have reported that the dc-link voltage of the GFM-WT can be regulated by either the grid-side converter (GSC) or the machine-side converter (MSC) [4]. For the case where GSC controls the dc-link voltage [9], [10], abbreviated as GFM-GWT, the dc-link voltage control is cascaded with the power-angle control, while the maximum power point tracking (MPPT) control is implemented with the MSC [11]. Due to the proven and mature MSC control, the control structure of the GFM-GWT emerges as an attractive solution [3]. The second approach, as introduced in [12], [13], abbreviated as GFM-MWT, utilizes the MSC to control the dc-link voltage through the torque regulation, while the GFM control is implemented in the GSC. This structure is particularly advantageous for achieving the island operation or black start of the WT, as the dc-link voltage can be regulated independently by the MSC when disconnected from the grid [14].

Many existing works that analyze the dynamics of GFM-WTs solely focus on the dynamics of the GFM control itself, where the mechanical dynamics of the turbine and drive train are often overlooked. [9] - [14]. It has been reported in [15] that torsional vibrations in GFM-MWTs can be triggered by grid-WT interactions, which can adversely affect the lifespan of turbine components and even generate electrical power oscillations that affect the stability of electrical grid [6].

Manuscript received 27 February 2024; revised 11 July 2024; accepted 10 August 2024.

The work is supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program through the Marie Skłodowska-Curie under Grant 861398. (Corresponding author: Xiongfei Wang, Heng Wu)

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Yet, the findings in [6], [15] are solely based on numerical simulation studies. Subsequent studies [8] have attempted to understand the influence of GFM controls on the damping ratio and damped frequency of torsional dynamics by developing a small-signal model and utilizing the complex torque method. However, these works are mainly focused on the GFM-MWT configuration. Thus, there is a lack of comparison between GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT in terms of their impacts on torsional dynamics.

Further, a systematic sensitivity analysis is essential to explicitly reveal how system parameters of GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT, i.e., electrical and mechanical system constants and controller gains, contribute to the torsional modes [16]. Previous studies, such as [17], [18], have performed sensitivity analyses on the impacts of specific parameters like SCR and C_{dc} , which are based on small-signal models at fixed operation points. Subsequent research [8] expanded this analysis to a broader range of system parameters for GFM-MWTs, including GFM control parameters. However, these analyses typically examined one parameter at a time. To overcome this drawback, the Partial Derivative Algorithm (PDA) based on the feedforward neural networks (FNN) is introduced as a promising approach, which stands out for quantifying the impact of varying system parameters simultaneously and providing a holistic view with all parameters included [19]. Therefore, the primary contributions of this paper are:

- The paper offers a comparative analysis of GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT in respect to their impacts on the damping ratio of torsional dynamics, which are based on small-signal models and complex torque coefficient method.
- Unlike the traditional sensitivity analysis that typically considers one parameter at a time while keeping others fixed, the FNN-based PDA enables a holistic evaluation of the impacts of multiple varying system parameters on torsional modes for GFM-WTs, particularly focusing on the revealing impacts on damped frequency.

This paper begins by establishing small-signal models for both GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT, as outlined in Section II. Subsequently, the complex torque coefficient method is employed in Section III to derive the expressions of damping ratio, natural frequency, and damped frequency for both GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT. Thereafter, the effect of various system parameters on the torsional dynamics is revealed in Section IV by utilizing the FNN-based PDA. Ultimately, electromagnetic simulations are performed to verify the theoretical findings, as detailed in Section V.

II. SMALL-SIGNAL MODELING OF ELECTROMECHANICAL DYNAMICS GFM-WT

A. System Description

The wind turbine is connected to the point of common coupling (PCC) via a back-to-back converter, which consists of an MSC, a GSC, and a dc-link capacitor C_{dc} . The turbine model includes 3-p blades connected to the rotor, a two-mass drive train, and a PMSG, equipped with pitch angle control and MPPT [20]. In this work, GFM-WTs are characterized

by two distinct configurations in respect to the dc-link voltage control

- GFM-GWT: The GSC regulates the dc-link voltage, as depicted in Fig. 2 (a).
- GFM-MWT: The MSC controls the dc-link voltage, as shown in Fig. 2 (b).

The detailed control structures for the MSC and GSC of the GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT are given in the following sections and depicted respectively, in Fig. 3 and Fig. 4.

1) *Control structure of GFM-GWT*: The detailed control diagram of the MSC in the GFM-GWT is depicted in Fig. 3 (a) [3], which is structured with an active power control as the outer loop and an inner loop for the current control. As the outer loop of the MSC for the GFM-GWT is used to achieve the MPPT control, the reference signal T_{genref} can be obtained by

$$T_{genref} = \frac{P_{ref}}{\omega_r} \quad (1)$$

where power reference P_{ref} are determined by the wind speed v_w and rotor speed ω_r , aligning with the optimal power curve [13].

The input of the current control loops is T_{genref} and outputs of the current control loops are the modulation signals v_{sdref} and v_{sqref} , as given by

$$\begin{aligned} v_{sdref} &= G_c(s)(i_{sdref} - i_{sd}) - \omega_r L_{dq} i_{sq} \\ v_{sqref} &= G_c(s)(i_{sqref} - i_{sq}) + \omega_r L_{dq} i_{sd} + \omega_r \psi_{pm} \\ i_{sqref} &= k_{Ti} T_{genref} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where,

$$\begin{aligned} G_c(s) &= k_{cP} + \frac{k_{cI}}{s} \\ k_{Ti} &= \frac{1}{1.5\psi_{pm}} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

L_{dq} represents the stator inductor, and ψ_{pm} is the magnetic flux, which is a constant value produced by the permanent magnets in PMSG and can be obtained from the nameplate data and generator parameters.

The GSC control scheme for the GFM-GWT, shown in Fig. 4 (a), is structured with a dc-link voltage control (DVC) and a reactive power control loop (RPC). According to [21], v_{dc}^2 is chosen as the reference signal for the DVC, and the transient power transfer of the dc-link capacitor is used to generate the angle of the ac output [22], which is expressed as

$$\theta = \frac{1}{s} [\omega_g + G_{dc}(s)(v_{dc}^2 - v_{dcref}^2)] \quad (4)$$

where v_{dcref} denotes the reference of dc-link voltage and θ is the reference angle. ω_g represents the grid fundamental angular frequency, while $G_{dc}(s)$ stands for the dc-link voltage controller,

$$G_{dc}(s) = k_{pdc} + \frac{k_{idc}}{s} \quad (5)$$

The reactive power is regulated by modifying the voltage [23], as detailed by

$$V_{dref} = V^* + K_q(Q_{ref} - Q) \quad (6)$$

$$V_{qref} = 0 \quad (7)$$

Fig. 2. Structural depiction of the GFM-WT (a) Configuration of GFM-GWT. (b) Configuration of GFM-MWT.

where Q_{ref} and V^* denote the reference of reactive power and nominal voltage magnitude, respectively. While V_{dref} represents the voltage reference at the d axis, which equals the voltage magnitude when the voltage reference at the q axis, V_{qref} , is 0. K_q signifies the reactive power-voltage droop coefficient [23].

2) *Control structure of MSC and GSC for the GFM-MWT:* The MSC for the GFM-MWT, as illustrated in Fig. 3 (b), also includes inner and outer control loops. Unlike the GFM-GWT, the GFM-MWT employs a DVC as the outer loop, as defined by

$$T_{genref} = \frac{G_{dc}(s)(v_{dcref}^2 - v_{dc}^2)}{\omega_r} \quad (8)$$

The comprehensive control scheme for the GSC for the GFM-MWT is depicted in Fig. 4 (b). The GSC in the GFM-MWT synchronizes with the power grid through active power control (APC), as described by

$$\theta = \frac{1}{s}[\omega_g - K_p P_o + \frac{1}{2Hs}(P_{ref} - P_o)] \quad (9)$$

where K_p and H stand for the active power-frequency droop and inertia coefficient, respectively.

Meanwhile, the RPC remains the same as in the GFM-GWT, as indicated by (7) [22].

The detailed development of a small-signal model for the GFM-MWT and GFM-GWT systems will be elaborated in the subsequent sections.

B. Small-signal modelling

1) *Aerodynamic wind energy conversion:* The wind turbine is configured with a three-blade connected to the rotor via a two-mass drive train [24], equipped with the MPPT control and pitch angle control [13]. The torque exerted by the wind turbine, T_{tur} , can be calculated by

$$T_{tur} = \frac{1}{2}\rho\pi R^3 C_t(\lambda, \beta) v_w^2 \quad (10)$$

where $C_t(\lambda, \beta)$ is the torque coefficient, which is given by

$$C_t(\lambda, \beta) = \frac{a_1}{\lambda} \left(\frac{a_2}{\lambda} - a_3\beta - a_4\beta^2 - a_6 \right) e^{-\frac{a_7}{\lambda}} \quad (11)$$

λ and β are the tip speed ratio and pitch angle respectively. The parameters R and ρ represent the radius of the turbine and the air density, respectively, whereas ω_t denotes the turbine rotational speed.

Fig. 3. Control block diagram of MSC for (a) The GFM-GWT. (b) The GFM-MWT.

Fig. 4. Control block diagram of GSC for (a) The GFM-GWT. (b) The GFM-MWT.

Assuming the GFM-WTs operate within the MPPT region ($4 \text{ m/s} < v_w < 11.68 \text{ m/s}$), which means $\beta = 0$, (10) can be linearized as

$$\hat{T}_{tur} = K_{tu\omega}\hat{\omega}_t + K_{tuv}\hat{v}_w \quad (12)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} k_{tu\omega} &= \left. \frac{dT_{tur}}{d\omega_t} \right|_0 = \frac{1}{2}\rho\pi R^3 v_{w0}^2 \left. \frac{dC_t(\lambda, \beta)}{d\lambda} \right|_0 \\ k_{tuv} &= \left. \frac{dT_{tur}}{dv_w} \right|_0 = \rho\pi R^3 v_{w0} C_t(\lambda_0, \beta_0) \\ &\quad + \frac{1}{2}\rho\pi R^3 v_{w0}^2 \left. \frac{dC_t(\lambda, \beta)}{dv_w} \right|_0 \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

The subscript 0 represents the operation point (steady state).

2) *Drive train*: In order to depict the torsional vibration mode, a two-mass drive train model is employed in this work. It is worth noting that the basic principles are applicable to any degree of complexity [25]. The motion equations for this model are described as

$$\begin{aligned} T_{tur} - T_{shaft} &= 2H_{wt}s\omega_t \\ T_{shaft} - T_{gen} &= 2H_g s\omega_r \\ T_{shaft} &= (d_s + \frac{k_s}{s})(\omega_t - \omega_r) \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where H_{wt} and H_g represent the inertia constants of the turbine and generator, respectively. The terms T_{tur} , T_{shaft} , and T_{gen} signify the mechanical, shaft, and electromagnetic torques, respectively. Additionally, k_s and d_s denote the stiffness and the damping coefficient of the shaft.

The small-signal representation of (14) can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{T}_{tur} &= 2H_{wt}s\hat{\omega}_t + (d_s + \frac{k_s}{s})(\hat{\omega}_t - \hat{\omega}_r) \\ -\hat{T}_{gen} &= 2H_g s\hat{\omega}_r - (d_s + \frac{k_s}{s})(\hat{\omega}_t - \hat{\omega}_r) \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

3) *MSC of the GFM-GWT*: Wind turbines convert mechanical to electrical power via an ideal PMSG [26]. According to [24], it is justifiable to assume that $T_{gen} \approx T_{genref}$ to reduce the system order to investigate the electromechanical dynamics of GFM-WTs.

The detailed control architecture for the MSC of the GFM-GWT is elaborated in (1), as depicted in Fig. 3 (a) [27], where P_{ref} can be expressed as

$$P_{ref} = \frac{1}{2}\rho\pi R^2 C_{opt} \frac{\omega_r^3 R^3}{\lambda_{opt}^3} \quad (16)$$

where C_{opt} signifies the coefficient of the optimal power performance, while λ_{opt} refers to the optimal tip speed ratio.

(16) can be further linearized as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{P}_{ref} &= K_m \hat{\omega}_r \\ K_m &= \left. \frac{dP_{ref}}{d\omega_r} \right|_0 = \frac{3}{2}\rho\pi R^2 C_{opt} \frac{\omega_{r0}^2 R^3}{\lambda_{opt}^3} \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

By linearizing (1), we can obtain

$$\hat{T}_{genref} = -K_{T\omega}\hat{\omega}_r + K_{TP}\hat{P}_{ref} \quad (18)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} K_{T\omega} &= \frac{P_{gen0}}{\omega_{r0}^2} \\ K_{TP} &= \frac{1}{\omega_{r0}} \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

By substituting (17) into (18), the small-signal representations of \hat{T}_{genref} can be formulated as

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{T}_{genref} &= (-K_{T\omega} + K_{TP}K_m)\hat{\omega}_r \\ &= \rho\pi R^2 C_{opt} \frac{\omega_{r0} R^3}{\lambda_{opt}^3} \hat{\omega}_r \end{aligned} \quad (20)$$

Considering $\hat{T}_{gen} \approx \hat{T}_{genref}$, for GFM-GWT, it can be concluded that

$$\hat{P}_{gen} \approx \hat{P}_{ref} \quad (21)$$

4) *MSC of the GFM-MWT*: The control structure of the MSC for the GFM-MWT is illustrated in Fig. 3 (b), where the reference signal for the outer loop is v_{dc}^2 [21], the controlled variable equation becomes

$$\frac{C_{dc}}{2} \frac{dv_{dc}^2}{dt} = P_{gen} - P_o \quad (22)$$

By linearizing (22), the small-signal representations of \hat{v}_{dc}^2 can be formulated as

$$\hat{v}_{dc}^2 = G_{up}(s)(\hat{P}_{gen} - \hat{P}_o) \quad (23)$$

where

$$G_{up}(s) = \frac{2}{sC_{dc}} \quad (24)$$

According to [24] and (8), the reduced-order model of the MSC control can be linearized as

$$\hat{P}_{gen} = G_{dc}(s)(\hat{v}_{dc}^2 - \hat{v}_{dc}^2) \quad (25)$$

Fig. 5. Electromechanical small-signal model of the GSC for (a) The GFM-GWT. (b) The GFM-MWT.

5) *GSC of the GFM-GWT*: Assuming the voltage magnitude constant to simplify the analysis [28], the linearized small-signal model of the GSC, derived from (4), is represented in (26). The corresponding small-signal model for the GSC is visually depicted in Fig. 5 (a).

$$\hat{\theta} = \frac{1}{s} [\hat{\omega}_g + G_{dc}(s)(\hat{v}_{dc}^2 - \hat{v}_{dc}^2)] \quad (26)$$

6) *GSC of the GFM-MWT*: Under the same assumption as for the GSC-GWT, the linearized small-signal interpretation of the GSC of GFM-GWT, derived from (9), is represented in (27). The corresponding small-signal model for the GSC is visually depicted in Fig. 5 (b).

$$\hat{\theta} = \frac{1}{s} [\hat{\omega}_g - K_p \hat{P}_o + \frac{1}{2Hs} (\hat{P}_{ref} - \hat{P}_o)] \quad (27)$$

7) *Grid*: The small-signal representation of the output active power P_o can be described by utilizing the quasi-static equation [29], which is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \hat{P}_o &= K_{\theta P} (\hat{\theta} - \hat{\theta}_g) \\ K_{\theta P} &= \frac{V_{g0} V_{o0}}{X} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

where V_{g0} and V_{o0} represent the line-to-line output voltage of the GSC and the grid, respectively. X denotes the line reactance between the GSC and the grid.

8) *Overall small-signal models of the GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT*: By combining the small-signal representation of the MSC, GSC, and turbine, the overall small-signal models of the GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT can be depicted as shown in Fig. 6 (a) and (b), respectively, where the 'Drive train' block represents the (15). According to Fig. 6 (a), it is clear that in the GFM-GWT, the part of the turbine and MSC works as a power supply for the whole system, and the sudden change of the grid cannot activate the torsional vibrations within the drive train. However, there is a feedback loop exists from $\hat{\omega}_r$ to \hat{T}_{gen} for the GFM-GWT, including the generator control, which may have an impact on the torsional modes of the wind turbine [11]. The corresponding transfer function of this feedback loop is formulated as shown in (20).

In contrast, for the GFM-MWT, as shown in Fig. 6 (b), it is obvious that there is a feedback loop exists from $\hat{\omega}_r$ to \hat{T}_{gen} for the GFM-WT, including the grid impedance, the MSC, the GSC, the generator, and the generator control. The corresponding transfer function of this feedback loop can be expressed as

$$\frac{\hat{T}_{gen}}{\hat{\omega}_r} = K_{TP} K_m G_{mwt} - K_{Tw} \quad (29)$$

where

$$G_{mwt} = \frac{G_{dc}(s) G_{up}(s)}{1 + G_{dc}(s) G_{up}(s)} \left(\frac{K_{\theta P}}{K_{\theta P} + 2K_{\theta P} K_p H s + 2H s^2} \right) \quad (30)$$

III. TORSIONAL MODE ANALYSIS

The torsional vibration analysis can be performed by characterizing the natural frequency ω_n , damping ratio ξ , and damped frequency ω_d of the torsional modes [30]. In this section, the ω_n , ξ , and ω_d of the inherent torsional modes of the drive train itself are analyzed first. Then, based on complete small-signal models of the GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT developed in Section. II, the impacts of GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT control schemes on torsional modes are further characterized by means of the complex torque coefficient method [31].

A. Torsional mode of the drive train

In this paper, a two-mass drive train model is utilized to depict the torsional vibration dynamics, as presented in (15). Assuming no external torques such that $\hat{T}_{tur} = \hat{T}_{gen} = 0$ [30], and substituting $\omega = s\theta$ into (15), the natural frequency,

parameters in Table. I, ω_{nt} , ξ_t and ω_{dt} are computed to be 2.5060 Hz, 0.0290, and 2.5050 Hz, respectively.

C. The application of the complex torque coefficient

Assuming $\hat{v}_w = 0$, (32) can be rewritten as

$$\hat{T}_{gen} = -W_M(s)\hat{\theta}_r \quad (34)$$

where

$$W_M(s) = \frac{2H_g s^2 + d_s s + k_s - (d_s s + k_s) \cdot (d_s - k_{tu\omega})s + k_s}{2H_{wt} s^2 + (d_s - k_{tu\omega})s + k_s} \quad (35)$$

According to [34], the torque \hat{T}_{gen} can be decomposed into two components

$$\hat{T}_{gen} = W_s(s)\hat{\theta}_r + W_d(s)\hat{\omega}_r \quad (36)$$

where $W_s(s)$ is the component of torque change in phase with the rotor angle perturbation $\hat{\theta}$ and is referred to as the synchronizing coefficient. While $W_d(s)$ is in phase with the speed deviation $\hat{\omega}$ and is referred to as the damping coefficient.

Under the Laplace-domain, (36) can be rewritten as

$$\hat{T}_{gen} = W_e(s)\hat{\theta}_r \quad (37)$$

where

$$W_e(s) = W_s(s) + sW_d(s) \quad (38)$$

$W_e(s)$ is the transfer function of the electrical network as described in (20) and (29). By substituting (37) into (34), we obtain

$$-W_M(s) = W_e(s) \quad (39)$$

Based on [31], for GFM-WTs, the natural frequency, ω_{nm} , can be obtained by solving

$$-W_{MR}(\omega) = W_s(\omega) \quad (40)$$

where $W_{MR}(\omega)$ is the real part of $W_M(j\omega)$.

After ω_{nm} is derived, the damping and synchronizing coefficients can be calculated to further obtain the damping ratio, ξ_m , and damped frequency, ω_{dm} , at the frequency of ω_{nm} . According to [31], the expressions of ξ_m and ω_{dm} can be simplified as

$$\xi_m = \frac{d_s(H_{wt} + H_g) - k_{tur}H_g + W_d(\omega_{nm})H_{wt}}{4H_{wt}H_g\omega_n} \quad (41)$$

$$\omega_{dm} = \omega_{nm}\sqrt{1 - \xi_m^2} \quad (42)$$

D. GFM-GWT

Based on Section. III-C, to obtain the torsional mode of the GFM-GWT by utilizing the complex torque concept, the small-signal model of the GFM-GWT can be further simplified as Fig. 7 (a). According to Fig. 7 (a), the synchronizing and damping coefficients, denoted as W_{sg} and W_{dg} respectively, of the GFM-GWT can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} W_{sg} &= 0 \\ W_{dg} &= K_m K_{TP} - K_{T\omega} \end{aligned} \quad (43)$$

(a) GFM-GWT

(b) GFM-MWT

Fig. 7. Small-signal models of GFM-WTs for torsional mode analysis. (a) GFM-GWT. (b) GFM-MWT.

By substituting (17) and (19), W_{dg} can be further expressed as

$$W_{dg} = \rho\pi R^2 C_{opt} \frac{\omega_{r0} R^3}{\lambda_{opt}^3} \quad (44)$$

where W_{dg} is a positive constant value regardless of varying system parameters.

As $W_{sg}(s) = 0$, the natural frequency of torsional mode for the GFM-GWT, denoted as ω_{ng} , remains the same as ω_{nt} . According to (41), the damping ratio of torsional mode for the GFM-GWT, represented by ξ_g , is given by

$$\xi_g = \frac{d_s(H_{wt} + H_g) - k_{tur}H_g + W_{dg}H_{wt}}{4H_{wt}H_g\omega_n} \quad (45)$$

Since the value of W_d is positive, ξ_g increases compared with ξ_t , which is the result of the utilization of the MPPT control. Subsequently, the increasing damping ratio leads to the slight decrease of damped frequency ω_{dg} as shown in (42). Given that $\omega_{ng} = \omega_{nt}$ and ξ_g is solely affected by the MPPT control, it is evident that the GSC control has no influence on the torsional modes, same as the behavior observed in traditional grid-following wind turbines.

E. GFM-MWT

As highlighted in Fig. 7 (b), the main difference between the torsional modes calculation for the GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT is the existence of $G_{mwt}(s)$. By analyzing the bode plot of $G_{mwt}(s)$, as shown in Fig. 8, it is observed that $G_{mwt}(s)$ exhibits typical low-pass filter characteristics with a cut-off frequency around 2 Hz.

By substituting (29) into (36), the synchronizing coefficient of the GFM-MWT, denoted as $W_{sm}(\omega)$, and the damping

 Fig. 8. Bode plot of $G_{mwt}(s)$.

coefficient of the GFM-MWT, $W_{dm}(\omega)$, can be obtained and presented in Fig. 9, where $W_{MR}(\omega)$ is also demonstrated. According to Section. III-C, the natural frequency of the torsional mode, denoted as ω_{nm} , can be solved by (40).

 Fig. 9. $W_s(\omega)$, $W_d(\omega)$ and $-W_{MR}(\omega)$ for the GFM-MWT.

As demonstrated by Fig. 9, $\omega_{nm} \approx \omega_{ng}$. Since ω_{nm} is larger than the cutoff frequency of $G_{mwt}(s)$, it is evident from Fig. 7 (b) that $W_{dm}(\omega_{nm})$ is dominated by $-K_T\omega$, as presented in Fig. 9, which implies that the GFM-MWT control system induces a negative damping effect on the torsional mode of the wind turbine, as delineated in (41).

As $W_{dm}(\omega_{nm}) < 0$ and $W_{dg} > 0$, it is clear that, among the two control schemes, employing the GFM-MWT can lead to more torsional vibrations. Regarding the natural and damped frequency, Fig. 9 shows the value of $W_{sm}(\omega)$ ranging around 0 and $W_{sg}(\omega) = 0$. Therefore, it is obvious that the control scheme has a limited impact on the natural frequency of the torsional mode. Since the natural frequency remains the same and $W_{dm}(\omega_{nm}) < W_{dg}$, (42) implies the value of ξ_m is slightly larger than the value of ξ_g due to the significantly small value of damping ratios.

Using the parameters provided in Table I, the damped frequency and damping ratio of torsional mode for the GFM-GWT, GFM-MWT, turbine and drive train are depicted in Fig. 10, which indicates that the damped frequency consistently hovers around 2.5 Hz. Furthermore, the order of the damping ratio for different setups is as follows: The GFM-GWT > Turbine > 2-mass drive train > The GFM-MWT.

The conclusion that the control scheme has a limited influ-

Fig. 10. Damped frequency and damping ratio for the 2-mass drive train, turbine, the GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT

ence on the natural frequency of the torsional mode remains valid within the existing parameter set for the drive train. Therefore, a more in-depth sensitivity analysis of how multiple system and control parameters influence the torsional modes of both GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT is provided in Section. IV, which aims to offer a comprehensive understanding of the impact of the control scheme on the torsional modes of GFM-WTs under various conditions.

IV. SENSITIVITY ANALYSIS

As summarized in Section II, the control and system parameters can influence the torsional modes of GFM-WTs and employing the GFM-MWT can lead to less damping ratio. However, the impact of each control and system parameter on the torsional mode, especially for damped frequency, remains unclear due to the complexity of the transfer function, as shown in (20) and (29). Hence, there are some researches on the sensitivity analysis. In [17], [18], the sensitivity analysis of SCR and C_{dc} are performed based on the small-signal model of GFM-WT. However, as illustrated in (20) and (29), the influence of one parameter is highly dependent on the operation point (the value of the other parameters), which means that the relationship should be non-linear. Besides, the variation of other parameters is not considered for that specific operation point. Therefore, it is essential to conduct a nonlinear sensitivity analysis based on a model that is able to calculate ξ_m and ω_{dm} according to parameters.

Fig. 11. Feedforward Neural Network (FNN)

Under this condition, the partial derivative algorithm (PDA) based on the Feedforward Neural Networks (FNN) model is proposed to gain a comprehensive understanding of how system and control parameters influence the torsional modes

TABLE II
 INPUTS AND OUTPUTS OF FNN

Inputs	x_1	x_2	x_3	x_4	x_5	x_6	x_7	x_8	x_9	x_{10}	x_{11}
	SCR	H	k_{pp}	k_s	H_g	H_{wt}	C_{dc}	v_w	d_s	k_{pdc}	k_{idc}
Range	1-10	2-7	0.01-0.04	200-500	0.4-1.6	1-3.5	0.05-0.5	4-10	1-2	0.39-1.4	0.43-1.7
Outputs	y_1 ξ_m					y_2 ω_m					

of the GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT under a non-linear-relationship. First, the FNN model is introduced to substitute the calculation process of ξ_m and ω_{dm} for the GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT, as illustrated in Fig. 11. Thereafter, the PDA is conducted based on the FNN for the torsional dynamics of GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT.

A. Feedforward Neural Networks

According to Section. II, ξ_m and ω_{dm} of GFM-WTs are affected by 11 control and system parameters, which are selected as inputs for the FNN, as illustrated in Table. II. While ξ_m and ω_{dm} are outputs y_1 and y_2 , as presented in Table. II. Fig. 11 shows the architecture of an FNN composed of n hidden layers and each hidden layer has m neurons. In our case, there are 5 hidden layers in total, and each layer has 512 neurons. The rectified linear unit (ReLU) is selected as the non-linear activation function, which means $f(x) = \max(0, x)$.

The information flowing inside the FNN unit is illustrated as Fig. 11 and the specific computations are shown as

$$\begin{aligned}
 h_k^1 &= f(o_k^1), o_k^1 = \sum_{i=1}^{11} w_{k,i}^1 x_i \\
 h_k^n &= f(o_k^n), o_k^n = \sum_{i=1}^m w_{k,i}^n h_i^{n-1} \\
 &\vdots \\
 y_k &= \sum_{i=1}^m w_{k,i}^6 h_i^5
 \end{aligned} \quad (46)$$

where x_i and y_i are the i th input and output variable. h_k^n denotes the k th hidden neurons from the n layer. While $w_{k,i}^n$ is the connection weight between the neurons from the $n-1$ layer and neurons in the n layer. o_k^n is the weighted sums of k th output neurons from the n layer.

For assessing the accuracy of the FNN model, the Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) is calculated, defined as

$$MAPE = \frac{100}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \frac{|a_i - f_i|}{|f_i|} \quad (47)$$

where a_i is the value from the small-signal model, as described in Section. II. While f_i denotes the value from the FNN model. After training with the data obtained based on Section. II, the MAPE for the GFM-GWT is 0.01%, as for the GFM-MWT, the MAPE is 0.16%.

B. Partial derivative algorithm

The PDA is a well-known neural network-based sensitivity analysis method [35]. Given that the FNN has been trained to a satisfactory level of accuracy, the PDA can be implemented to identify the variations of output parameters with respect to small changes in each input parameter. This can be done by calculating the Jacobian matrix that contains the partial derivatives of outputs with respect to inputs [19], defined as

$$S_{ki} = \frac{\partial y_k}{\partial x_i} \quad (48)$$

Beyond individual calculations, it is often beneficial to consider the average sensitivity across the entire dataset to understand the global influence of each input [35], expressed as

$$\bar{S}_{ki} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=1}^N \left| \frac{\partial y_k}{\partial x_i} \right|_N \quad (49)$$

where \bar{S}_{ki} represents the average sensitivity of input x_i on the output y_k , and N is the total number of observations.

For each input, the sensitivity percentage P_{ki} can be used as a factor for classification of the influence on the output y_k of the neural network model, which is given by

$$P_{ki} = \frac{\bar{S}_{ki}}{\sum_{i=1}^{11} \bar{S}_{ki}} \quad (50)$$

Therefore, the most important or crucial input parameter has the highest value of P_{ki} . The sensitivity analysis results of the inputs on outputs for the GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT are presented in Fig. 12 and Fig. 13, separately.

Fig. 12. Sensitivity analysis of the inputs of the GFM-GWT on (a) damping ratio (b) damped frequency.

Fig. 12 (a) shows that the damping ratio of the GFM-GWT is highly sensitive to the system parameters v_w , d_s , H_g , k_s and H_{wt} . while the control parameters of GSC and MSC have very limited impact on ξ_g . As demonstrated in Fig. 12 (b), the damped frequency is primarily influenced by H_g , k_s , and H_{wt} . The results indicate that mechanical parameters dominate the characteristics of torsional modes for

Fig. 13. Sensitivity analysis of the inputs of the GFM-MWT on (a) damping ratio (b) damped frequency.

GFM-GWT. Therefore, careful selection and tuning of these parameters can substantially improve stability.

As illustrated in Fig. 13 (a), the ξ_m is highly sensitive to H_{wt} , v_w , d_s , H_g and moderately sensitive to H , k_s , k_{pp} , C_{dc} , k_{pdc} , SCR. As for the damped frequency, it is shown in Fig. 13 (b) that ω_{dm} is still primarily influenced by H_g , k_s , and H_{wt} . The results reveal clearly that both mechanical and electrical parameters influence the damping ratio of torsional modes for GFM-MWT, while the damped frequency of torsional modes is still mainly decided by the mechanical parameters.

V. VALIDATION THROUGH NONLINEAR TIME-DOMAIN SIMULATIONS

Fig. 14. Comparison of simulation results and small-signal models for disturbance response of ω_r and P_o with 2° step disturbance adding to θ_g under steady state. (a) GFM-GWT. (b) GFM-MWT.

In order to validate the small-signal model of the GFM-WT for torsional vibration analysis under θ_g changes, the time-domain simulations are carried out in MATLAB/Simulink and

Fig. 15. Comparison of simulation results and small-signal models for disturbance response of ω_r and P_o with 0.4 m/s step disturbance adding to v_w under steady state. (a) GFM-GWT. (b) GFM-MWT.

PLECS blockset with the detailed electronic model presented in Fig. 2. The parameters given in Table I are adopted.

To verify the small-signal model, the simulation result for disturbance response of ω_r under grid-side phase angle and wind speed disturbance are compared with the results from the small-signal model, as shown in Fig. 14 and Fig. 15.

Fig. 14 illustrates the non-linear time domain simulation results for disturbance response of ω_r and P_o for GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT under 2° step disturbance in θ_g at steady state, where the maxim error compared with the small-signal model is approximately $1.24e^{-4}$ p.u. for GFM-GWT and $2.75e^{-4}$ p.u. for GFM-MWT. It is clear that the grid-side phase change can activate the torsional dynamics within GFM-MWT but not for GFM-GWT. Moreover, the activated torsional dynamics can eventually affect the output power of the GFM-MWT on the grid side.

While Fig. 15 illustrates the non-linear time domain simulation results for disturbance response of ω_r and P_o for GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT with 0.4 m/s step disturbance adding to v_w under steady state, where the maxim error compared with the small-signal model is approximately $1.12e^{-4}$ p.u. for GFM-GWT and $2.50e^{-4}$ p.u. for GFM-MWT. Besides, a higher amplitude of oscillations can be observed for GFM-MWT compared with GFM-GWT, which influences the output power on the grid side.

In summary, the grid-side dynamics can activate the torsional dynamics within GFM-MWT but not for GFM-GWT. On the other hand, the wind speed disturbance can activate torsional vibrations for both GFM-GWT and GFM-MWT. However, the GFM-MWT control leads to a less damping

effect on torsional vibrations compared with GFM-MWT.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has discussed the impacts of converter control strategies, with a particular focus on the implementation of dc-link voltage control, on the torsional dynamics of GFM-WTs. The complex torque method based on the reduced-order small-signal model has been used to derive expressions for the damping ratio and damped frequency to provide a clear insight into the first-degree torsional modes of GFM-WTs. It is revealed that the GFM-MWT control has an adverse impact on the damping ratio of the torsional mode of the GFM-WT, which is a consequence primarily driven by the DVC of MSC. In contrast, the GFM-GWT control enhances the damping ratio of the torsional mode. Furthermore, the study also uncovers the influence of all control and system parameters on damping ratio and damped frequency of torsional modes by utilizing FNN-based PDA. More specifically, it is pointed out that the damped frequency of torsional modes for GFM-WT is dominated by mechanical design regardless of varying control parameters. The simulation results validate the theoretical findings.

For wind turbine manufacturers, understanding the adverse impact of GFM-MWT control on the damping ratio can inform better design choices, particularly in selecting and configuring converter control strategies to enhance torsional stability. For grid operators, these insights can aid in developing more robust integration strategies for GFM applications, ensuring stability and reliability in the grid. Future research could focus on exploring advanced control strategies that mitigate the adverse impacts identified, such as adaptive or predictive control methods. In summary, this research enhances the understanding of torsional dynamics when integrating GFM-WTs into the grid for future stability and reliability-focused research and applications.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The work is supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Program through the Marie Skłodowska-Curie under Grant 861398.

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VII. BIOGRAPHY SECTION

Shiyi Liu (S'21) received B.S. and M.S. degrees in Electrical Engineering and Automation from North China Electric Power University, in the year 2015 and 2018 respectively. From June 2021 to June 2024, she worked as an Early Stage Researcher within the Marie Skłodowska-Curie ITN project "WinGrid" at the DNV. She was also pursuing the Ph.D. degree in Electrical Engineering with the Department of Energy (AAU Energy), Aalborg University, Denmark. Since July 2024, she has been working as a Policy Advisor at TenneT TSO B.V.

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